

UMBRA: A semi-analytical umbrella-cloud source term for tephra dispersal modeling — formulation, implementation, and preliminary inversion

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Abstract

Estimating eruption source parameters (ESPs) from tephra-fall deposits is important for eruption reconstruction and hazard assessment. For large explosive eruptions ($VEI \geq 4$), lateral spreading of umbrella clouds near the neutral buoyancy level can exert a first-order control on tephra dispersal, yet most semi-analytical transport models do not represent this process explicitly. When applied to umbrella-forming deposits, such models may compensate through inflated diffusion coefficients and release heights, yielding ESP estimates that are difficult to interpret physically. This report presents UMBRA, a reduced-order framework that couples a physics-based umbrella-cloud source term with an advection-diffusion-sedimentation solver. The source term is derived from gravity-current similarity theory and uses a survival function to represent grain-size-dependent particle loss as the cloud spreads and thins. Applied to the Pululagua ~ 2450 BP eruption (Ecuador), the coupled model provides a good first-order fit to the observed deposit (72 sites; $\log\text{-RMSE} = 0.16$) using diffusion coefficients of 200–300 m^2/s , substantially lower than those required by earlier static-source inversions of the same dataset. Two independent inversion algorithms (grid search and multi-start simplex) converge toward the same solution family, with erupted mass near 1.95×10^{11} kg and MER near 2.3×10^8 kg/s. The source-term geometry also shows good first-order agreement with published satellite observations and independent numerical simulations of the 1991 Pinatubo eruption. These results support UMBRA as a promising inversion-ready prototype for umbrella-cloud tephra dispersal, while broader validation and formal uncertainty quantification remain future steps. The code is open-source and intended for desktop-scale ensemble workflows.

1. Introduction

Tephra fall deposits are the primary geological record of explosive volcanic eruptions. Reconstructing the eruption source parameters (ESPs) that produced a given deposit, such as erupted mass, mass eruption rate (MER), eruption duration, plume height, umbrella cloud dimensions, and total grain-size distribution (TGSD), is central to both volcanological research and hazard forecasting. In practice, ESPs can be estimated through a range of approaches. The simplest rely on empirical analysis of deposit geometry: fitting exponential, power-law, or Weibull thinning functions to isopach and isopleth data and integrating to obtain volume and mass estimates (e.g., Fierstein and Nathenson, 1992; Bonadonna and Houghton, 2005; Bonadonna and Costa, 2012). These methods are widely used and require no forward model, but they yield point estimates without uncertainty quantification and cannot recover parameters like MER or TGSD directly.

A more physics-based approach is to fit a forward transport model to the observed deposit. Semi-analytical advection-diffusion-sedimentation (ADS) solvers represent the eruption column as a set of stacked point sources distributed along a vertical line (or diffused along it through empirical coefficients), and transport particles to the ground under prescribed wind and isotropic turbulent diffusion (e.g., Suzuki, 1983; Macedonio et al., 2005; Bonadonna et al., 2005; Connor et al., 2019). Models in this family,

including Tephra2 (Bonadonna et al., 2005; Connor et al., 2019) and HAZMAP (Macedonio et al., 2005), have been applied to dozens of eruptions over the past two decades for both forward hazard assessment and inverse ESP estimation (e.g., Scollo et al., 2008; Bonasia et al., 2010; Constantinescu et al., 2024). For small to moderate eruptions, these models perform well. They are fast, the physics is tractable, and the source geometry is a reasonable approximation of the real eruption column.

For large eruptions ($VEI \geq 4$), tephra dispersal is not dominated by vertical fallout but by the lateral spreading of an umbrella cloud at the neutral buoyancy level. This cloud can extend hundreds of kilometers from the vent within hours, transporting ash radially outward as a gravity current before particles settle through the atmosphere (e.g., Sparks et al., 1997; Costa et al., 2013; Mastin and Van Eaton, 2020). Standard ADS solvers with sub-vertical source geometries cannot represent this lateral transport. When forced to fit deposits from umbrella-forming eruptions, they compensate by using high diffusion coefficients K and effective plume heights H , because H and K work in tandem to explain the widespread dispersal: a higher release altitude increases wind advection while a larger K spreads the Gaussian kernel. Constantinescu et al. (2021) demonstrated this effect quantitatively, showing that fitting the Pululagua 2450 BP eruption deposit with a static disk source required $K \approx 9500 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, an order of magnitude above typical atmospheric eddy diffusivities ($100\text{--}500 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$). The practical consequence is that fitted K and H no longer represent their nominal physical quantities; they become proxy parameters that absorb the missing umbrella transport, and the resulting ESP estimates are difficult to interpret.

Constantinescu et al. (2021) took a first step toward addressing this problem in semi-analytical ADS models, by replacing the standard sub-vertical line source in Tephra2 with a static disk at umbrella altitude. The disk distributes mass uniformly across a circular (or elliptical) area at a prescribed height, representing the umbrella cloud as a fixed, time-independent source. Applied to Pululagua, this approach showed that the umbrella radius, rather than column height, is the primary control on sedimentation patterns for large eruptions. However, the disk geometry is still static: all particle sizes are distributed uniformly, and the umbrella is fitted independently rather than derived from eruption dynamics.

At the other end of the spectrum, full numerical models such as FALL3D (Costa et al., 2006; Folch et al., 2020) and Ash3D (Schwaiger et al., 2012) can simulate umbrella dynamics explicitly. These models discretize the governing equations in three dimensions and resolve the time-evolving cloud structure. Their computational cost, however, makes them impractical for ensemble workflows on a typical desktop station. Such models require thousands of forward simulations, such as Bayesian inversion or probabilistic hazard mapping, and often require the use of High Performance Computing (HPC) (e.g., Montesinos et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2026).

This report describes UMBRA (Umbrella-cloud Modeling for Bayesian Reconstruction and Hazard Analysis), a reduced-order framework that extends the static-disk approach of Constantinescu et al. (2021) into a time-evolving, physics-based umbrella source term. Instead of distributing mass uniformly across a fixed disk, UMBRA represents the umbrella cloud as a gravity current that spreads, thins, and loses particles in a grain-size-dependent manner according to established similarity theory (Costa et al., 2013). This dynamic source term is then coupled to an ADS solver for particle transport to the ground. Because lateral mass redistribution is treated explicitly in the source term, the diffusion coefficient can

remain within typical atmospheric values, and H is interpreted as the altitude of umbrella spreading or the base of the umbrella cloud rather than plume top. A full forward simulation runs in seconds on a laptop, making the framework suitable as an inversion-ready prototype and benchmark tool rather than a replacement for full 3D dispersal models.

The report is organized as follows. Section 2 derives the mathematical formulation of the umbrella source term. Section 3 describes the ADS solver and the settling velocity models available. Section 4 presents verification tests (symmetry, mass conservation, and source term behavior under wind). Section 5 applies the coupled framework to a preliminary inversion of the Pululagua ~2450 BP eruption and discusses the results, including parameter identifiability and the implications of the fitted ESPs. Section 6 discusses limitations and planned developments. The code and full documentation are available at [Zenodo DOI].

2. Mathematical Formulation of the Umbrella Source Term

2.1 Gravity-current spreading

The umbrella cloud is modeled as an axisymmetric gravity current spreading radially at the neutral buoyancy level (NBL). The formulation follows the similarity theory of Costa et al. (2013), building on the classic framework for density-driven intrusions in stratified environments (Huppert and Simpson, 1980; Sparks et al., 1997; Suzuki and Koyaguchi, 2009).

Costa et al. (2013) coupled this analytical spreading model with FALL3D by superimposing a time-dependent radial velocity field onto the meteorological wind, allowing the Eulerian transport model to capture gravity-driven cloud expansion directly. UMBRA takes a different approach: rather than modifying the wind field at runtime, the spreading dynamics are resolved analytically through a survival function (Section 2.4), which provides a static, grain-size-resolved source distribution to the ADS solver. This avoids the need for time-stepping the cloud evolution within the transport model, at the cost of not resolving transient cloud structure during the eruption.

The volumetric flux of material entering the umbrella from the eruption column is:

$$Q = C\sqrt{k_e}\dot{M}^{3/4}N^{-5/4} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{M} is the mass eruption rate [kg/s], N is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency of the atmosphere at the NBL [s^{-1}], k_e is the entrainment coefficient, and C is an empirical constant that depends on the latitude of the eruption. Following the erratum of Costa et al. (2013), $C \approx 430 m^3 kg^{-3/4} s^{-3/2}$ for tropical eruptions and $C \approx 870 m^3 kg^{-3/4} s^{-3/2}$ for mid-latitude and polar eruptions. For a steady eruption with total mass M_0 and duration T , the MER is simply $\dot{M} = M_0/T$.

Under the inertia-buoyancy spreading regime, the cloud radius grows as:

$$R(t) = At^{2/3} \quad (2)$$

where the spreading coefficient is:

$$A = \left(\frac{3\lambda NQ}{2\pi} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

and λ is a dimensionless shape factor for the gravity current. Typically $\lambda \approx 0.2$ based on direct numerical simulations (e.g., Suzuki and Koyaguchi, 2009). At the end of the eruption ($t = T$), the circular umbrella radius in the absence of wind is:

$$R_{\text{circ}} = AT^{2/3} \quad (4)$$

The mean thickness of the cloud decreases with time as it spreads:

$$\bar{h}(t) = \frac{\lambda Q}{\pi A^2} t^{-1/3} \quad (5)$$

This expression follows from volume conservation: the cumulative volume fed into the cloud up to time t is Qt , and the cloud area is $\pi R^2 = \pi A^2 t^{4/3}$, so $\bar{h} = Qt/(\pi A^2 t^{4/3})$.

Figure 1. Idealized umbrella cloud source geometry. The umbrella cloud (gray disk) spreads laterally at the neutral buoyancy level H , with thickness h . The cloud is discretized into grid cells that release tephra from their centers. Particles settle from the cloud base through the atmosphere to the ground. Adapted from Constantinescu et al. (2021).

2.2 Particle trajectories within the cloud

To track particles within the spreading cloud, we introduce a dimensionless radial coordinate $\xi = r/R(t)$, where r is the radial distance from the vent and $R(t)$ is the cloud front at time t . A fluid

parcel entering the cloud at time τ arrives at the front when $t = \tau$, giving $\xi = 1$ at that moment. At any later time $t > \tau$, the parcel has been overtaken by the expanding front and sits at some $\xi < 1$.

We adopt the trajectory ansatz:

$$\xi^2 = 1 - \frac{\tau}{t} \quad (6)$$

This is a closure assumption, not a result derived from the full shallow-water equations. It states that a parcel entering at time τ moves outward such that ξ^2 increases linearly from 0 (at $t = \tau$, when the parcel is at the front) to 1 as $t \rightarrow \infty$. In physical terms, it implies that older fluid is progressively left behind as the cloud expands, concentrated toward the interior.

From this ansatz and the spreading law $R = At^{2/3}$, one can derive the radial velocity profile.

Differentiating $r = \xi R(t)$ with respect to t at fixed τ :

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \frac{d\xi}{dt}R + \xi \frac{dR}{dt}$$

Using $dR/dt = (2/3)At^{-1/3}$ and differentiating Eq. (6), the velocity of a fluid parcel can be expressed as:

$$v_r(\xi) = \frac{2}{3}At^{-1/3}f(\xi) \quad (7)$$

where the dimensionless velocity profile is:

$$f(\xi) = \frac{3 + \xi^2}{4\xi} \quad (8)$$

This profile is not assumed a priori; it follows uniquely from the trajectory closure and the $t^{2/3}$ spreading law. It satisfies $f(1) = 1$ (parcels at the front move at the front speed) and $f(\xi) > \xi$ for $\xi < 1$.

2.3 The settling-spreading ratio

For each grain-size class i with terminal settling velocity $w_{s,i}$ [m/s], we define a dimensionless settling-spreading ratio:

$$K_i = \frac{3\pi}{4} \frac{A^2 w_{s,i}}{\lambda Q} \quad (9)$$

K_i quantifies the competition between particle settling and cloud thinning. When K_i is large (coarse particles, high $w_{s,i}$), the settling rate exceeds the rate at which the cloud thins, and particles are lost from the cloud rapidly. When K_i is small (fine particles), settling is slow relative to thinning and particles remain suspended across most of the cloud radius.

2.4 The survival function

The survival function $S_i(\eta, r)$ gives the fraction of particles of class i that remain in the cloud at a radial position corresponding to the dimensionless coordinate $\eta = r/R_b$, where R_b is the local cloud boundary (equal to R_{circ} for a no-wind case, or the azimuth-dependent boundary under wind). It is obtained by integrating the settling loss along the particle's trajectory through the cloud.

A particle of class i released into the cloud at time τ settles through the local cloud thickness $\bar{h}(t)$ with velocity $w_{s,i}$. The fraction of the cloud thickness traversed by time t is the settling integral:

$$I_i(\tau, t) = \int_{\tau}^t \frac{w_{s,i}}{\bar{h}(t')} dt'$$

Substituting $\bar{h}(t')$ from Eq. (5) and evaluating:

$$I_i(\tau, t) = \frac{3\pi A^2 w_{s,i}}{4\lambda Q} [t^{4/3} - \tau^{4/3}]$$

Using the trajectory relation $\tau = t(1 - \xi^2)$ from Eq. (6) and evaluating at the end of the eruption:

$$S_i(\eta, r) = \exp \left\{ -K_i \frac{r^2}{\eta^2 A^2} \left[1 - (1 - \eta^2)^{4/3} \right] \right\} \quad (10)$$

For large K_i (coarse particles), S drops steeply with distance: most mass settles out within a few kilometers of the vent. For small K_i (fine particles), S remains near unity across the full cloud radius (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Survival function $S_i(r)$ for selected grain-size classes, showing the fraction of particles remaining suspended within the umbrella cloud as a function of radial distance from the vent. Coarse particles ($\phi = -4$, (16 mm)) are depleted within ~ 25 km; fine ash ($\phi = +4$, (0.062 mm)) remains largely in suspension across the full cloud radius ($R_{\text{circ}} \approx 37$ km, dotted vertical line). This size-dependent radial sorting is the core mechanism distinguishing UMBRA from static-source approaches, where all grain sizes are distributed uniformly. Parameters correspond to the Pululagua best-fit configuration (Section 5).

2.5 Areal mass density and in-cell loss

The mass arriving at a given point within the cloud, per unit area, combines the areal arrival density (ρ_{arrival}) with the survival function. For grain-size class i with mass fraction f_i in the TGSD:

$$\rho_{\text{arrival}, i}(\eta, r) = \frac{\dot{M}_i \eta^2}{\pi r^2} \quad (11)$$

where $\dot{M}_i = f_i \dot{M}$ is the mass flux of class i entering the cloud. The factor η^2/r^2 accounts for the geometric concentration toward the cloud center.

The fraction of mass deposited within a grid cell of linear dimension Δ at radial distance r is captured by the in-cell loss factor:

$$L_i = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{3\pi}{2} \frac{w_{s,i}}{\lambda Q} \frac{\Delta_\ell r}{f(\eta) \eta}\right) \quad (12)$$

where $\Delta_\ell = \pi s/4$ is the mean chord length across the cell and s is the cell side length. The mean chord $\pi s/4$ is used rather than an angle-dependent chord because the latter introduces a grid-related artifact: - a four-fold pattern in azimuth with no physical basis.

2.6 Per-cell source mass and mass conservation

The mass attributed to a given grid cell is obtained by integrating the product of the survival function, the arrival density, and the in-cell loss over the annular range of arrival coordinates η that contribute to the cell, and over the cell area:

$$m_{j,i} = \frac{1}{\Delta^2} \iint_{\text{cell } j} \left[\int_{\eta_0}^1 S_i \rho_{\text{arrival},i} L_i \left| \frac{d\tau}{d\eta} \right| d\eta \right] dx dy \quad (13)$$

The outer integral (over the cell footprint) is evaluated by Gauss-Legendre quadrature at a configurable order (typically 5 points per dimension). The inner integral (over η) is evaluated by Gauss-Legendre quadrature over the range $[\eta_0, 1]$.

Mass conservation is enforced explicitly by per- ϕ normalization:

$$\hat{m}_{j,i} = m_{j,i} \times \frac{f_i M_0}{\sum_j m_{j,i}} \quad (14)$$

The normalization factor $\alpha_i = f_i M_0 / \sum_j m_{j,i}$ is a diagnostic. Values in the range 50–300 are typical for the $S \times L$ formulation and reflect the mathematical structure of the integrand.

2.7 Wind deformation

Under nonzero wind at the umbrella altitude, the circular cloud is deformed into an ellipse following the approach of Bonadonna and Phillips (2003). The cloud center is displaced downwind and the vent sits at one focus of the ellipse.

The downwind and upwind extent of the cloud are:

$$R_{\text{down}} = R_{\text{circ}} + U T \quad (15)$$

If $T \leq t^*$:

$$R_{\text{up}} = R_{\text{circ}} - U T \quad (16 \text{ a})$$

If $T > t^*$:

$$R_{\text{up}} = \frac{4}{27} \frac{A^3}{U^2} \quad (16 \text{ b})$$

where U is the wind speed at the umbrella altitude and $t^* = \left(\frac{2A}{3U}\right)^3$ is the stall time. The ellipse parameters follow from R_{down} and R_{up} :

$$a = \frac{R_{down} + R_{up}}{2}, \quad e = \frac{R_{down} - R_{up}}{R_{down} + R_{up}}, \quad b = a\sqrt{1 - e^2} \quad (17)$$

The azimuth-dependent cloud boundary is given by the focal-polar form:

$$R_b(\theta) = \frac{p}{1 - e \cos \theta} \quad (18)$$

where $p = b^2/a$ is the semi-latus rectum and θ is the polar angle measured from the downwind direction. To conserve total mass under the elliptical deformation, the source field is scaled by a focusing factor $F = \langle R_b^2 \rangle / R_b^2$, applied per cell as a function of azimuth.

2.8 Summary of parameters

Table 1. Summary of model parameters, their typical ranges, and how they are constrained.

Symbol	Parameter	Typical range	How constrained
M_0	Total erupted mass	$10^{10} - 10^{14} \text{ kg}$	Inverted from deposit
T	Eruption duration	$10^2 - 10^5 \text{ s}$	Inverted or from observations
H	Umbrella spreading altitude (NBL)	8–25 km asl	Inverted or assigned
r_{inner}	Inner exclusion radius	1–5 km	Prescribed (plume-corner proxy)
N	Brunt-Väisälä frequency	$0.01 - 0.025 \text{ s}^{-1}$	From atmospheric profile or ISA
k_e	Entrainment coefficient	0.05 – 0.12	Published range
λ	Gravity current shape factor	0.20 – 0.24	DNS calibration
C	Volumetric flux constant	430 (tropical), 870 (mid-lat)	Latitude-dependent (Costa et al., 2013, erratum)
ϕ_{med}, σ_ϕ	TGSD parameters	Variable	Inverted or assumed
U, θ_w	Wind speed and direction at NBL	Variable	From reanalysis or profile
$w_{s,i}$	Terminal settling velocity per class	$10^{-3} - 10^1 \text{ m/s}$	Computed from drag law + particle properties

3. The ADS Solver

3.1 Transport model

The ground-level mass loading from a point source releasing particles at altitude H into a steady, horizontally uniform wind field is given by the classical ADS solution (Suzuki, 1983; Bonadonna et al., 2005):

$$m_i(x, y) = \frac{M_{s,i}}{4\pi K_i \tau_i} \exp \left[-\frac{(x - x_s - \Delta x_i)^2 + (y - y_s - \Delta y_i)^2}{4K_i \tau_i} \right] \quad (19)$$

where $M_{s,i}$ is the source mass for grain-size class i released at position (x_s, y_s) , τ_i is the fall time from release height to the ground, $(\Delta x_i, \Delta y_i)$ is the cumulative horizontal drift during descent, and K_i is the isotropic diffusion coefficient. The total ground mass loading at any observation point is obtained by summing Eq. (19) over all active source cells j and grain-size classes i .

This is the same formulation used by Tephra2 (Bonadonna et al., 2005; Connor et al., 2019) and applied with an umbrella disk source by Constantinescu et al. (2021). The present implementation differs in three aspects, described below.

3.2 Altitude-resolved trajectory integration

Rather than using column-averaged wind, the fall time and horizontal drift for each grain-size class are computed by integrating the particle descent trajectory through the full altitude-resolved wind profile:

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = -w_{s,i}(z), \quad \frac{dx}{dt} = u(z), \quad \frac{dy}{dt} = v(z) \quad (20)$$

where $w_{s,i}(z)$ is the terminal settling velocity evaluated at the local air density $\rho_{air}(z)$ and dynamic viscosity $\mu_{air}(z)$ from the International Standard Atmosphere (ISA), and $u(z)$, $v(z)$ are the wind components interpolated from an input profile at altitude z . When observation sites have different elevations, trajectories are interpolated to each site's local ground altitude from cumulative arrays stored during a single downward pass.

3.3 Diffusion

A dual- K scheme assigns different diffusion coefficients based on fall time:

- $K = K_{coarse}$ if $\tau_i < fall - timethreshold$
- $K = K_{fine}$ if $\tau_i \geq fall - timethreshold$

Values used here are $K_{coarse} = 200 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and $K_{fine} = 300 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, consistent with atmospheric turbulent diffusion. K is not a free parameter in the inversion.

3.4 Settling velocity and particle density

Terminal settling velocities are computed via an iterative drag coefficient-Reynolds number scheme. Four drag-law options are available: Stokes (laminar reference), Schiller-Naumann with shape correction (following Pfeiffer et al., 2005), Ganser (1993), and Bagheri and Bonadonna (2016). Three particle density models are supported: constant, step-function, and sigmoidal blend (Eychenne and Le Penec,

2012). For the Pululagua application, we use Schiller-Naumann drag ($F_s = 0.64$) and sigmoidal density ($\rho_{coarse} = 600, \rho_{fine} = 2600 \text{ kg/m}^3$). See the code documentation for full implementation details.

3.5 Grid-mode acceleration

For regular ground grids with uniform elevation, the Gaussian kernel is replaced by its cell-integrated form using the error function:

$$P_x = \frac{1}{2} \left[\operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x + \Delta/2 - x_{land}}{\sigma} \right) - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{x - \Delta/2 - x_{land}}{\sigma} \right) \right] \quad (21)$$

where Δ is the cell width, x_{land} is the particle landing position, and $\sigma = \sqrt{4K\tau}$. The 2D kernel is separable: $P_{xy} = P_x \cdot P_y$. Convolution is performed via FFT.

4. Verification

4.1 Zero-wind symmetry

The coupled framework was run with zero wind speed to verify radial symmetry. With $U = 0 \text{ m/s}$, the deposit contours are circular to within numerical precision, with anisotropy index $AI \approx 0$. This verifies correct implementation of the source geometry, the ADS kernel, and the grid alignment (the vent is anchored at a grid node to prevent centering artifacts).

4.2 Mass conservation

For the Pululagua configuration ($M_0 = 1.95 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg}$, grid resolution 1 km), the closure error between deposited and erupted mass is below 0.1%. The redistribution factors α_i range from approximately 50 to 300 across the grain-size spectrum, confirming that the normalization step (Eq. 14) compensates exactly.

4.3 Source term verification under wind: Pinatubo

The source term module was run with parameters corresponding to the climactic phase of the 1991 Pinatubo eruption ($M_0 = 2 \times 10^{13} \text{ kg}$, $T = 9 \text{ h}$, $U = 10 \text{ m/s}$ toward 235° , $H = 25 \text{ km}$, $N = 0.02 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $C = 430$). The modeled umbrella footprint (Fig. 3B) closely matches satellite-derived outlines from GMS imagery (Fig. 3A, after Holasek et al., 1996), the Ash3D simulation of Mastin and Van Eaton (2020; Fig. 3C), and the FALL3D coupled gravity-current simulation of Costa et al. (2013; Fig. 3D). This verifies the wind-deformation scheme and confirms plausible geometries at VEI 6 scale. The full deposit simulation for Pinatubo is planned as part of ongoing validation.

Figure 3. Umbrella cloud extent for the 1991 Pinatubo eruption. (A) Satellite-derived outlines of the growing umbrella cloud on 15 June 1991, digitized from GMS imagery after Holasek et al. (1996), reproduced from Mastin and Van Eaton (2020). (B) UMBRA source term showing the modeled cloud geometry after 9 h of eruption; colors indicate the cumulative mass released from each location within the umbrella (source field, not ground deposit). (C) Ash3D simulation from Mastin and Van Eaton (2020) using the same eruption parameters. (D) FALL3D simulation coupled with the gravity current model from Costa et al. (2013), showing simulated cloud PM₁₀ column mass at successive times. The UMBRA footprint in panel B shows good first-order agreement with the published umbrella geometries and supports the plausibility of the wind-deformation implementation at VEI 6 scale. This comparison is intended as a source-term verification rather than a full deposit validation.

5. Application: Pululagua Inversion

5.1 Dataset

The Pululagua ~2450 BP eruption (Ecuador) produced a near-circular tephra deposit under low-wind conditions, suitable for testing the umbrella source term without wind advection complications. The dataset consists of 72 mass-loading observations from Constantinescu et al. (2021), with site elevations ranging from approximately 1600 to 3250 m asl. The same dataset was used in the 2021 static-disk inversion, which fitted the deposit with erupted mass of 2.5×10^{11} kg, umbrella radius 10 km, umbrella height 25 km, and diffusion $K = 9500$ m²/s. Pululagua is used here as a development benchmark and proof-of-concept case because it is well constrained, inversion-ready, and only weakly affected by wind; it is not presented as full validation across the entire range of umbrella-forming eruptions.

5.2 Inversion setup

The inversion searches over total erupted mass M_0 , umbrella spreading altitude H , and eruption duration T , with H interpreted as the altitude of umbrella spreading / neutral buoyancy rather than plume top. The inner radius r_{inner} was prescribed at 1000 m as a conservative structural parameter representing the unresolved near-source transition between column-fed and umbrella-fed fallout. Sensitivity tests showed that, within physically reasonable ranges, the best-fit basin is controlled primarily by mass, duration, and spreading height ($\Delta\chi^2 < 0.08$). The TGSD was fixed (median $\phi = 1.0$, $\sigma_\phi = 1.6$). Wind was set to zero. Two independent algorithms were applied:

1. Grid search: 9 levels for mass ($1.7 - 2.7 \times 10^{11}$ kg), 9 for height (10–14 km), 9 for duration (300–1800 s), and 5 for r_{inner} (1–3 km), giving 3645 forward evaluations.
2. Multi-start Nelder-Mead simplex: Six independent starts with initial points jittered from the center of the grid range; three starts seeded from top grid results. Each start allowed 80 iterations.

The objective function is the log-space chi-square:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{obs}}} w_k \left[\log_{10}(m_k^{\text{mod}}) - \log_{10}(m_k^{\text{obs}}) \right]^2 \quad (22)$$

The logarithmic transform ensures that proximal and distal sites contribute comparably, given that mass loading spans more than one order of magnitude.

5.3 Results (Figs. 4 and 5)

Both algorithms converge to the same solution basin. The best-fit parameters are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Best-fit eruption source parameters for the Pumulagua inversion from the grid search and multi-start simplex algorithms. Both methods converge to the same solution basin. MER is derived as M_0/T , not inverted independently.

Fit metrics for the grid-search best trial: $\log\text{-RMSE} = 0.162$, $\text{NRMSE} = 0.34$, $\text{bias} = 0.002$.

Figure 4. Modeled vs. observed mass loading for the Pululagua best-fit solution (grid search). The dashed orange line is the 1:1 reference. Points above the line indicate model overprediction; below, underprediction. All 72 observation sites are shown. $\log\text{-RMSE} = 0.162$, $\text{bias} \approx 0$.

Figure 5. Radial thinning profile for the Pululagua best-fit solution. Black circles: observed mass loading at each field site; blue diamonds: modeled values at the same locations. The scatter at any given distance reflects azimuthal variation in the deposit. The model, being radially symmetric under zero wind, threads a mean through this scatter. The overall first-order thinning trend from $\sim 350 \text{ kg/m}^2$ near the vent to $\sim 10 \text{ kg/m}^2$ at 29 km is well captured.

5.4 Identifiability

Within the explored Pululagua search domain, duration is the best-constrained individual parameter. Mass is moderately constrained, with overshoot penalized more steeply. $MER (= M_0/T)$ emerges as the best-constrained composite parameter: the misfit minimum lies along a diagonal ridge of approximately constant MER near $\approx 2.3 \times 10^8 \text{ kg/s}$. Height is constrained near $H = 10 \pm 0.5 \text{ km}$, where H represents the umbrella spreading altitude (NBL proxy), not plume top. The inner radius shows negligible sensitivity and is appropriately prescribed.

5.5 Spatial residual structure

The residual map (Fig. 6) reveals a systematic pattern. Proximal sites and the northern sector are well fitted, with residuals generally below 0.1. The western flank (sites PL52–54, 12–25 km from vent) shows observed mass loadings 2–4.5 times higher than modeled values. In a no-wind inversion with a radially symmetric source, this azimuthal asymmetry is consistent with a residual wind component, and motivates future inversions with wind as an active parameter.

Figure 6. Spatial residual map for the Pululagua best fit. Each circle represents one of the 72 observation sites, colored by $\log_{10}(\text{modeled}/\text{observed})$. Green tones indicate good agreement; yellow indicates overprediction; dark blue/purple indicates underprediction. The western flank of the deposit (left side) shows systematic underprediction, possibly reflecting a residual wind component during the eruption. The vent is located near the origin (0, 0).

5.6 Physical interpretation: the R_{circ} discrepancy

For the best-fit parameters ($M_0 = 1.95 \times 10^{11} \text{ kg}$, $T = 863 \text{ s}$, $H = 10 \text{ km}$), the similarity law (Eqs. 1–4) gives $R_{circ} \approx 35 \text{ km}$. This is substantially larger than the 10 km umbrella radius fitted by Constantinescu et al. (2021) using a static disk source on the same dataset.

This discrepancy does not necessarily indicate a calibration problem. The 10 km static-disk radius is a mass-weighted effective radius: it places all erupted mass uniformly across a disk, and the inversion finds the disk size that minimizes the misfit. In UMBRA, the survival function concentrates mass near the vent (because coarse particles settle out quickly) and distributes progressively less mass toward the periphery. A physically larger cloud can therefore produce the same deposit footprint as a smaller uniform disk. This result illustrates quantitatively why static and dynamic source representations yield different ESP estimates for the same deposit.

Figure 7. Misfit landscape for the Pululagua inversion: erupted mass vs. duration, at the best-fit height ($H = 10$ km), marginalized over r_{inner} . Colors show the χ^2 objective in log-space. Black star: grid search best fit ($\chi^2 = 1.892$); white circle: simplex best fit ($\chi^2 = 1.896$). White dashed lines are isolines of constant MER. The minimum lies at $MER \approx 2.3 \times 10^8$ kg/s, with a diagonal trade-off ridge: higher mass compensates with longer duration to maintain approximately constant MER.

6. Discussion

6.1 Diffusion coefficient

Perhaps the most practical outcome is that the Pululagua deposit can be reproduced with diffusion coefficients of 200–300 m^2/s . The 2021 inversion required $K \approx 9500$ m^2/s . The explanation is that in a static-source model, diffusion is the only mechanism for spreading mass laterally. If the deposit extends further than the source disk, K must increase to spread the Gaussian kernel wide enough. In UMBRA, the umbrella source term handles the redistribution, and diffusion only accounts for turbulent spreading during particle descent. The practical consequence is that the principal ESPs become less entangled with the transport parameterization than in the static-source formulation. In the present prototype, mass, duration, and spreading height each retain a more direct physical interpretation, although complete decoupling cannot yet be claimed.

6.2 Limitations

The trajectory ansatz (Eq. 6) is a closure assumption; the full shallow-water equations would give a somewhat different velocity profile. Whether this introduces significant bias is an empirical question to be addressed by comparison with 3D simulations. The spreading exponent of $2/3$ assumes an inertia-buoyancy regime throughout; Prata et al. (2025) suggest alternative regimes for some eruption phases. No particle aggregation is included, though a first-order mass-reassignment scheme is planned. The MER is assumed steady within each eruption phase. These limitations define the next development targets rather than undermining the feasibility of the current demonstrator.

6.3 Outlook

Next steps include calibration against the 1991 Pinatubo eruption (a VEI 6 test case in wind conditions), independent validation on the Rungwe eruption (VEI 5, Tanzania), and ensemble-based uncertainty quantification for the AD 79 Vesuvius deposit using *pestpp-ies* (White, 2018; Constantinescu et al., 2024). The complete source code, configuration files, and the Pululagua observation dataset are available at [Zenodo DOI].

7 References

- Bagheri, G. and Bonadonna, C. (2016). On the drag of freely falling non-spherical particles. *Powder Technology*, 301, 526–544.
- Bonadonna, C. and Costa, A. (2012). Plume height, volume, and classification of volcanic explosive eruptions based on the Weibull function. *Bull. Volcanol.*, 75(742), 1–19.
- Bonadonna, C. and Houghton, B. (2005). Total grain-size distribution and volume of tephra-fall deposits. *Bull. Volcanol.*, 67(5), 441–456.
- Bonadonna, C., Connor, C. B., Houghton, B. F., Connor, L., Byrne, M., Laing, A., and Hincks, T. K. (2005). Probabilistic modeling of tephra dispersal: Hazard assessment of a multiphase rhyolitic eruption at Tarawera, New Zealand. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 110(B3).
- Bonadonna, C. and Phillips, J. C. (2003). Sedimentation from strong volcanic plumes. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 108(B7).
- Bonasia, R., Macedonio, G., Costa, A., Mele, D., and Sulpizio, R. (2010). Numerical inversion and analysis of tephra fallout deposits from the 472 AD sub-Plinian eruption at Vesuvius. *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 197(1–4), 98–110.
- Connor, C. B., Connor, L. J., Bonadonna, C., Luhr, J., Savov, I., and Navarro-Ochoa, C. (2019). Modelling Tephra Thickness and Particle Size Distribution of the 1913 Eruption of Volcán de Colima, Mexico. In: Varley, N., Connor, C., Komorowski, J.-C. (eds) *Volcán de Colima. Active Volcanoes of the World*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-25911-1_3
- Constantinescu, R., Hopulele-Gligor, A., Connor, C. B., Bonadonna, C., Connor, L. J., Lindsay, J. M., et al. (2021). The radius of the umbrella cloud helps characterize large explosive volcanic eruptions. *Commun. Earth Environ.*, 2(1), 3.

- Constantinescu, R., White, J. T., Connor, C. B., Hopulele-Gligor, A., Charbonnier, S., Thouret, J.-C., et al. (2022). Uncertainty Quantification of Eruption Source Parameters Estimated From Tephra Fall Deposits. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 49(6), e2021GL097425.
- Constantinescu, R., White, J. T., Connor, C., Cole, P., Fontijn, K., Barclay, J., and Robertson, R. (2024). Estimation of eruption source parameters for the 2021 La Soufrière eruption (St Vincent). *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, 539(1), SP539-2023-2038.
- Costa, A., Folch, A., and Macedonio, G. (2006). A three-dimensional Eulerian model for transport and deposition of volcanic ashes. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.*, 241(3), 634–647.
- Costa, A., Folch, A., and Macedonio, G. (2010). A model for wet aggregation of ash particles in volcanic plumes and clouds: I. Theoretical formulation. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, B09201.
- Costa, A., Folch, A., and Macedonio, G. (2013). Density-driven transport in the umbrella region of volcanic clouds: Implications for tephra dispersion models. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 40(18). [Erratum 2019].
- Costa, A., Mingari, L., Smith, V. C., Macedonio, G., McLean, D., Folch, A., and Yun, S.-H. (2024). Eruption plumes extended more than 30 km in altitude in both phases of the Millennium eruption of Paektu (Changbaishan) volcano. *Commun. Earth Environ.*, 5(6), 1–13.
- Costa, A., Folch, A., Suzuki, Y. J., Mingari, L., and Macedonio, G. (2026). Eruption source parameters in volcanic plume modeling: Advances, challenges, and future directions. *Rev. Geophys.*, 64, e2025RG000897.
- Eychenne, J. and Le Pennec, J.-L. (2012). Sigmoidal particle density-size distribution in the deposits of Tungurahua volcano. *Bull. Volcanol.*, 74, 929–940.
- Fierstein, J. and Nathenson, M. (1992). Another look at the calculation of fallout tephra volumes. *Bull. Volcanol.*, 54, 156–167.
- Folch, A., Costa, A., Durant, A., and Macedonio, G. (2010). A model for wet aggregation of ash particles in volcanic plumes and clouds: II. Model application. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, B09202.
- Folch, A., Mingari, L., Gutierrez, N., Hanzich, M., Macedonio, G., and Costa, A. (2020). FALL3D-8.0: A computational model for atmospheric transport and deposition of particles, aerosols and radionuclides - Part 1: Model physics and numerics. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 13, 1431–1458.
- Ganser, G. H. (1993). A rational approach to drag prediction of spherical and nonspherical particles. *Powder Technol.*, 77(2), 143–152.
- Holasek, R. E., Self, S., and Woods, A. W. (1996). Satellite observations and interpretation of the 1991 Mount Pinatubo eruption plumes. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 101(B12), 27635–27655.
- Huppert, H. and Simpson, J. (1980). The slumping of gravity currents. *J. Fluid Mech.*, 99, 785–799.
- Macedonio, G., Costa, A., and Longo, A. (2005). A computer model for volcanic ash fallout and assessment of subsequent hazard. *Computers and Geosciences*, 31(7), 837–845.
- Mastin, L. G. and Van Eaton, A. R. (2020). Comparing Simulations of Umbrella-Cloud Growth and Ash Transport with Observations from Pinatubo, Kelud, and Calbuco Volcanoes. *Atmosphere*, 11(10), 1038.

- Montesinos, B. M., Luzón, M. T., Sandri, L., et al. (2022). On the feasibility and usefulness of high-performance computing in probabilistic volcanic hazard assessment. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 10, 941789.
- Prata, F., Prata, A. T., Tanner, R., Grainger, R. G., Borgas, M., and Aubry, T. J. (2025). The radial spreading of volcanic umbrella clouds deduced from satellite measurements. *Volcanica*, 8(1), 1–29.
- Schwaiger, H. F., Denlinger, R. P., and Mastin, L. G. (2012). Ash3d: A finite-volume, conservative numerical model for ash transport and tephra deposition. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117(B4), B04204.
- Scollo, S., Folch, A., and Costa, A. (2008). A parametric and comparative study of different tephra fallout models. *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 176(2), 199–211.
- Sparks, R. S. J., Bursik, M. I., Carey, S. N., Gilbert, J., Glaze, L. S., Sigurdsson, H., and Woods, A. (1997). *Volcanic Plumes*. Wiley, Chichester.
- Suzuki, T. (1983). A theoretical model for dispersion of tephra. In: Shimozuru, D. and Yokoyama, I. (Eds.), *Arc Volcanism: Physics and Tectonics*, pp. 95–116. Terra Scientific Publishing, Tokyo.
- Suzuki, Y. J. and Koyaguchi, T. (2009). A three-dimensional numerical simulation of spreading umbrella clouds. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 114(B3), B03209.
- White, J. T. (2018). A model-independent iterative ensemble smoother for efficient history-matching and uncertainty quantification in very high dimensions. *Environ. Model. Softw.*, 109, 191–201.